

Hyderabad Karnataka Librarians'
Association

A Study of Information Seeking Behaviour of Science Students at Government Institutions in Karnataka (India)

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ABSTRACT

The study focuses on the information need and searching behaviour of Post Graduate (P.G.) students of different faculty of Science at Government College, Kalaburagi, one of the largest Government Academic Institute of Karnataka. The data collected from a sample of 196 students adopting questionnaire as well as personal interview method. The study finds the present status of information need, problem affecting the information seeking behaviour and future requirements of the students for exploring the e-resources available globally.

Keywords – Information need, Information seeking behaviour, e-resources, Library facilities

1. INTRODUCTION

Information can be considered in general term, essentially required to develop a human being differing from person to person according to one's need. Information for students for higher education and research is on the other hand is much focused and has a purpose of achieving their goals in life using the enormous resources available in the era of information technology.

Information seeking behaviour and information need are some of the fundamental areas of the library researchers to provide suggestions for the up gradation and digitization of the library to make the library popular amongst students for seeking relevant information with an ease in a helpful and conducive environment.

It is an effort to identify and analyze the trends in the information seeking behaviour of Post Graduate Students in Government College Kalaburagi. As Kalaburagi is the hub of education and the students from different part of the state are enrolled in the college, so the college can be taken as a sample Government Institute of Karnataka (India). In the study summary data on the

information seeking behaviour of target group is presented and the practical significance of the data is analyzed.

2. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The objectives of the study are

- Examine the STUDY OF Information Need and Seeking Behaviour of Science students in P.G library,
- Identify the purpose of visiting library by students
- Understand the time spent on reading activities in the library
- Frequency of using various information sources concerned to law discipline and Level of Satisfaction towards Information sources available in the library

3. ABOUT THE GOVERNMENT COLLEGE AND CENTRAL LIBRARY

Government College, Kalaburagi, presently affiliated to the Gulbarga University, was founded in 1932.. This is the oldest college of Kalaburgai (North Karnataka) with magnificent Artitectural Heritage, spread over 30 acres of land, boasts of a multi faculty co-education post graduate studies in 05 Departments with 60 faculty members and about 2500 regular enrolments, viz Physics, Mathematics, Zoology and Computer Science and Microbiology having 50 faculty members and more than 2000 students, are running in the college these departments have approx.. The college outreaches to the widest range of rural as well as urban youth. Significant number of its students is rural, remotely inhabited and first generational learners. Government College, Kalaburagi is one of the leading centers of academic excellence caters to the educational needs of the society located in the backward region of Hyderabad Karnataka. The college has been accredited with 'A' Grade by NAAC in 2012. Library is an integral part of the college it makes sincere efforts to assure an environment for intellectual inquiry by providing user focused services to meet the curriculum needs of the students and teaching faculty with its rich information sources.

The central library of the college is one of the oldest library in Karnataka, With the seating capacity of 200 visitors. The library remains open since 10 AM to 5 PM in all working days. The library provides access to specialized information resources and services to meet the academic and research information needs of the reading community by developing specialized need based collection; organizing information resources; providing access to information. Besides, 1,38,289 printed collection, 500 + Video Lectures Recorded and provided by Commissioner Department of Collegiate Education, Bengaluru. The library has now access to N-LIST e-resources covering 3800 + e-journals (Including Current with 10 Years Back files) and 80,000 + e-books for the benefit of the students and teaching community. College Library subscribes to the well known national and international journals in humanities, social sciences and Science. Recently college has purchased e-lib software to full automate the functioning of library. College library is headed by well qualified and experienced librarian. Dr. J Nagamma is having Ph.D. in library science. She has been awarded with ' Best Librarian Award ' by Govt. Of Karnataka in 2014 for her dedication and service to the library. Besides her 2 Attenders and 1 peon works after the day to day activities of the library with utmost dedication and sincerity.

4. METHODOLOGY

Experimental Design : This study was designed as an exploratory study of the information need and information seeking behaviour of Post Graduate Students and Research

Scholars of Science stream in Government College Kalaburagi. To serve the dual purpose of information need and seeking behaviour, questionnaire and personal interview method was adopted. Total 230 questionnaires were distributed and filled by each individual. A total number of 196 completed and submitted for the analysis. The survey has yielded quantitative data on each question to convey a real picture regarding the factor triggering the information need, individual concept and thought and seeking behaviour.

Data Analysis : the questionnaire containing 16 questions were distributed, which covers almost all the aspects of the information seeking behaviour of the target group. 200 questionnaire were distributed to P.G. student and 170 (85 %) were received by them.

5. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

It is clear that the entire respondents have habit to use the library services. It is evident from the data that 91.77 % are dependent on the library for updation of knowledge and for review of literature. But most of the P.G. students (91.77 %) with the library for book transaction, book bank service and to get literature of new topic introduced in syllabus.

Table 1: Frequency of library visit

Frequency of visit the library	P.G. Student (%)
Always (Daily)	106 (62.36)
Frequently	50 (29.41)
Some time	14 (8.23)
Never	0 (0)

Table 2: Satisfaction with library hours

Category of user	Fully (%)	Not Satisfied (%)	Not Comment (%)	Partially (%)
P.G.Student	119 (70)	11(6.47)	13(7.64)	27 (15.88)

Library timing of this institute is official time (10.00 AM To 5.00 PM). Most of the stake holders are satisfied with the library timings except some who want the resource material whenever they require. Some of the the P.G. students living in hostels that the library hours should be extended, so that they can access the literature in those hours with least rush.

Table 3: The collection of books

Category of user	Need (%)	Sufficient (%)	Not sufficient (%)	Improvement (%)
P.G.Student	17 (10)	44 (25.88)	75 (44.11)	34 (20)

Though the college library has sufficient number of books in all subjects but still there is need of more books. Most of the require improvement in all sense i.e. subscription of more journals, access of more e-resources but the survey of P.G. students indicate that collection of books is not sufficient so more number of books required for contemporary knowledge.

Table 4: Satisfaction with the library services

Category of user	Yes (%)	No (%)	Partially (%)	Fully (%)	Some time (%)
P.G.Students	69(40.58%)	19 (11.17%)	55(35.35%)	21(12.35%)	6(3.52%)

Regarding the satisfaction with library services is fully satisfied with the services in the category. But a number of P.G. students are fully satisfied as the literature is fully available according to their curriculum. It is also reflected from the feedback that the library should improve the services as a good number of the respondents are not satisfied.

Table 5: Use of information sources

Source	P.G.Student (%)
Discussion with the teachers/research guide	40 (23.53)
Discussion with the colleagues within the organization	19 (11.17)
An article in a periodical	13 (7.64)
Journals	10 (5.88)
Books	20 (11.76)
Internet	14 (8.23)
Library & Information center	52 (31.18)
Any other	2 (1.17)

A question to assess the specific seeking behaviour is asked in questionnaire. Though the teachers provide the initial information but Library and Information centers are the most preferable and reliable sources to get any information for the research scholars. The trend varies in case of the P.G.students. for P.G. students the priority is the completion of curriculum hence they access various sources of information. But in this case also the Library and information center is the most preferable source.

Table 6: Time spent in a week to get information from the various sources

Source of information	Time spent		
	Upto 5 hrs	6 to 10 hrs	10 hours & more
Reading Text Books	70 (41.1)	20 (11.7)	12 (7.5)
Reading Reference Resources	60(35.2)	28 (16.4)	6 (3.5)
Reading News Paper	130(76.4)	12 (7.05)	0 (0)
Net surfing	125(73.5)	15 (8.82)	15 (8.82)
Access e-resources	90(52.9)	19 (11.1)	9 (5.2)

Above table portrays the number of hours students spend to get information from various sources in library in a period of a week. Majority of the P.G. students remain in library less than 5 hours. In case of the facilities is given for individual access of e-resources (N-LIST and DELNET), so they can access the same from anywhere. But the P.G. students spend a significant time in library for e-resources. The results also reflect that the information seeking behaviour is shifting from traditional ways (issue and return of books, book search for the study material) to the modern technologies (net access etc.).

Table 7: Library use before joining the institute

Category of user	Yes (%)	No (%)
P.G.Student	144 (84.70)	26 (15.29)

This question was asked to find out that the students are habitual in use the library from the previous classes. The results are unexpected. Almost 15 % P.G. students did not use the library services before. This is because of the following reasons –

- i. Popularity of passbook / One week Series (short book containing question and answer)- the students from rural background mainly rely on this type of material
- ii. Admission mainly for scholarship purpose – some of the students of under privileged category (Scheduled Caste/ Scheduled Tribe/ Other Backward Class / Minorities) take admission in the college to get the benefit of Government Schemes like scholarship / stipend etc.
- iii. Book bank facilities in the library is also one of the reasons which prohibit the students to avail regular library facilities.

Table 8: Primary purpose of seeking information

S.No.	Category of user	Responses Received
		P.G.Student (%)
1	Career Development	48 (28.23)
2	General	7 (4.11)
3	Project/Research	15 (8.82)
4	To keep up to date	20 (11.76)
5	Higher Studies	30 (17.64)
6	Preparation of examination/completion of curriculum	50 (29.41)

Career development is a prominent issue for P.G. students and libraries are serving well in this regard. But the trends of other purposes are different the P.G. students come in the library to get the material to complete their curriculum and to get information regarding their higher studies.

Table 9: Level of convenience in using ICT facilities in library

Sources of Informatio	Highly Convenient (%)	Convenient (%)	Slightly Convenient (%)	In convenient –
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n				(%)
	P G S	P G S	P G S	P G S
Computer	35(20.5)	50(29.41)	31(18.2)	15(8.82)
e-journal	25(14.7)	61(35.88)	20(11.7)	0(0)
DELNET	38(22.3)	53(31)	28(16.47)	18(10.58)
INFLIBNET	21(12.35)	50(29.41)	33(19.41)	0(0)
Internet	28(16.47)	62(36.47)	19(11.17)	0(0)

ICT facilities are commonly used in library services and most of the students are satisfied with them also. Most of the libraries use static IP addresses on their ICT means to avoid misuse and economic access. But in the world of changing technology the expectations of the students are much higher and need more facilities like access of e-resources on dynamic IP instead of Static IP, so that they can access more resources on their own gadgets. It is also reflected from the study that the DELNET facility is more convenient than the INFLIBNET.

Table 10: Visit library for various purposes

Purpose	Daily (%)	2-3 days in a week (%)	Weekly (%)	Fortnightly (%)	Monthly (%)
	P.G.S	P.G.S	P.G.S	P.G.S	P.G.S
Borrowing Books	0(0)	20(11.7)	50(29.4)	120(70.5)	0(0)
Access Periodicals	30(17.6)	40(11.7)	20(11.7)	15(8.8)	0(0)
Access Reference Resource	6(3.5)	95(55.88)	25(14.7)	19(11.1)	12(7.05)
Reading News paper	90(52.9)	20(11.7)	15(8.8)	0(0)	0(0)
Internet Surfing	70(41.1)	25(14.7)	28(16.4)	15(8.8)	9(5.2)
Access e-resources	50(29.4)	15(8.8)	22(12.9)	9(5.2)	25(14.7)

Users visit the library for various purposes. Majority of the daily visitors are of P.G.students who mainly come for the newspaper reading and Internet surfing visit the library daily to access reference resources and e-resources. as the library has fortnightly schedule of book borrowings, so most of the students kept the books for the scheduled span.

Table - 11 difficulties usually face in seeking required information

Area / field	Always (%)	Sometimes (%)	Never (%)
	P.G.Students	P.G.Students	P.G.Students
Lack time	90(52.9)	64(37)	11(6.15)
Paucity publication	8(4.7)	72(42)	15(8.82)

Lack literature	25(14.07)	126(74)	26(15.29)
Lack of library services	84(49.41)	58(34.1)	15(8.82)
Scattered sources of information	12(7.05)	55(32.3)	16(9.41)

Respondents were asked to indicate the problems faced by them while seeking the required information. Most of P.G student pointed out that they sometimes face the following problems. As P.G. students remain busy with the regular classes and the practical work so lack of time is the main issue for not visiting the library. The lack of library services / staff is the main cause of the difficulties.

6. CONCLUSION

The study finds out that maximum user in habit to visit the library. The results from the study based on the analysis clearly show that Post Graduate students seeks for information in relation to their academic and research needs. The services and the available resources at the library of Government College Kalaburagi are being used optimally by the science students, but the expectations are more in this world of knowledge. The resources mostly consulted by postgraduate are the text or reference books. Only few consult the periodicals and project while library and abstracting journal remains the popular tools used in accessing information sources. N-LIST (INFLIBNET) facility is highly convenient for PG students. But computer e-journal, e-books and other electronic data is not sufficient. In this era of Information and communication technology, where Internet has revolutionized every facet of library system, it is very important that library personnel working in the various libraries should as a matter of urgency embraced the reality of ICT if they are to remain relevant to the information conscious society.

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